

HOOP guidance for the organisation of National Replication Workshops

ACR+

The HOOP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N°101000836

Document information

Project Title	Hub of circular cities bOOsting Platform to foster investments for the valorisation of urban biowaste and wastewater
Project Acronym	HOOP
Grant Agreement No.	101000836
Project Call	CE-FNR-17-2020
Project Duration	48 months: 1 October 2020 – 30 September 2024
Project URL	https://hoopproject.eu/
Work Package	8
Deliverable	D8.3
Lead Partner	ACR+
Contributing Partner(s)	ACR+
Dissemination level	Public
Contractual delivery date	30 th September 2021
Actual delivery date	22 nd September 2021
Author(s)	Serena Lisai & Jean-Benoit Bel
Reviewer(s)	Carina Diedrich & Fiona Woo (CSCP); Mar Escarrabill (SfC); Miguel Ángel Suárez & Elisa Gambuzzi (CETENMA)
Document history	V1 shared with selected partners on 09/07/2021 V2 shared with WP Leaders 01/09/2021 V3 shared with Project Coordinator 15/09/2021

Disclaimer

This document reflects the views of the author(s) and does not necessarily reflect the views or policy of the European Commission. Whilst efforts have been made to ensure the accuracy and completeness of this document, the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains nor for any errors or omissions, however caused. This document is produced under [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](#).

Table of contents

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
2. INTRODUCTION	7
2.1. The HOOP Project.....	7
2.2. The HOOP Network of Cities and Regions	7
3. THE NATIONAL REPLICATION WORKSHOPS	9
3.1. What is a National Replication Workshop?	9
3.2. The objectives.....	10
3.3. Stakeholders to be involved	10
3.4. HOOP partners in support	11
4. HOW-TO GUIDE TO ORGANISE A NATIONAL REPLICATION WORKSHOP.....	13
4.1. Step 1: Define the key topics and objectives	13
4.2. Step 2: Identify the stakeholders.....	14
4.3. Step 3: Involve experts.....	15
4.4. Step 4: Define the format	16
4.5. Step 5: Draft the agenda	18
4.6. Step 6: Promotion.....	18
4.7. Step 7: The results.....	19
5. CONCLUSIONS	21
6. REFERENCES	22

7. ANNEX23

7.1. Check list.....23

7.2. The HOOP partners26

The HOOP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N°101000836

List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
ACR+	Association of cities and regions for the sustainable resource management
BC	Biowaste Club
CSCP	Collaborating Centre on Sustainable Consumption and Production
GIE	Greenovate! Europe
NRW	National Replication Workshop
PDA	Project Development Assistance
SCP	Sustainable patterns of consumption and production
SfC	Science for Change
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
UCBH	Urban Circular Bioeconomy Hub
UNEP	United Nations Environment Program

1. Executive summary

The HOOP project aims to unlock bio-based investments and deploy local bio economies in Europe through a systemic and cross-cutting approach. It will offer project development assistance to a group of 8 Lighthouse Cities and Regions (from now on Lighthouses) to build the technical, economic, financial and legal expertise needed to develop concrete investments to valorise biowaste and wastewater, with the aim of obtaining safe and sustainable bio-based products.

Actually, the EU Bioeconomy Strategy sees cities becoming major circular bioeconomy hubs, where biowaste is a feedstock for safe and sustainable bio-based products, but until now very few cities and regions have developed circular bio-based economy strategies or projects for the production of innovative bio-based products. Within the urban bioeconomy concept, biowaste and wastewater are considered a resource and converted into products such as bio-fertilisers and bio-plastics. As a result, they remain in the flow of materials following the principle of circular economy. The HOOP project aims to foster investment and implementation of urban biowaste and wastewater valorisation projects.

This report is one of the outputs of the HOOP project and it aims at guiding the Lighthouses involved in the in the organisation of National Replication Workshops (NRW). Each lighthouse is in charge of organising at least one NRW over the course of the project to promote the replication of the HOOP findings to other cities and regions at national level, and push forward innovative solutions for local bioeconomy strategies. This how-to guide will be a tool to inspire methodologies and activities for the organisation of NRW, yet Lighthouses will be given flexibility to make it relevant and effective. Transforming an idea in reality is the goal of the HOOP project and the NRW represents a key element to demonstrate how local bioeconomy concept can be turned into actual projects.

The first part of this report is a short introduction about the HOOP project and the National Replication Workshops, the goals to achieve and how they should be inserted in the project activities. Then, a how-to guide is provided to define step-by-step the elements that should be considered in advance for the organisation of such an event. The guide provides suggestions and inspirations to organise the workshops keeping in mind that the approach chosen needs to be adapted to the national context. Therefore, this guide is more a source of inspiration listing various possibilities and approaches that can be then selected to make the most of the event. The guide can be adapted and replicated in every context and sector.

The report also contains a ready-to-use toolkit as annexes: a check list of the activities to implement, with a reference to the time, the people to involve and the status.

2. Introduction

2.1. The HOOP Project

The [HOOP project](#) supports eight Lighthouse Cities and Regions to develop large-scale urban circular bioeconomy initiatives that will focus on making bio-based products from urban biowaste and wastewater.

Namely, HOOP will provide Project Development Assistance (PDA) to Albano Laziale (Italy), Almere (The Netherlands), Bergen Region (Norway), Kuopio (Finland), Münster (Germany), Murcia (Spain), Greater Porto (Portugal), and Western Macedonia (Greece).

The [HOOP Network of Cities and Regions](#) aims to facilitate exchange of knowledge and mutual learning among cities and regions willing to recover valuable resources from urban biowaste and wastewater to make bio-based products.

By joining the network, cities and regions can gain information on innovative urban bioeconomy solutions, and engage in activities relevant to their context and specific interests. Participants also have direct exchanges with the eight HOOP Lighthouse Cities and Regions, sharing their experiences and expertise.

2.2. The HOOP Network of Cities and Regions

The [HOOP Network of Cities and Regions](#) aims to bring together cities and regions outside of the consortium that are invited to follow the project's development, participate in open meetings and share their difficulties and experiences with one another. The main objective is to establish a European network to facilitate the exchange of good practices related to urban bioeconomy among cities and regions and to promote the replication of HOOP outcomes across Europe.

More specifically, the HOOP Network of Cities and Regions aims to:

- Disseminate the project's outcomes to as many European cities and regions as possible;
- Promote exchanges between the consortium and European cities and regions, e.g., by involving them in capacity building events, but also by taking advantage of their experience for the project's activities and outcomes;
- Promote exchanges among HOOP Lighthouse cities and regions and other European cities and regions, and among territories belonging to the HOOP network, taking advantage of the Urban Circular Bioeconomy Hub.

Here, "cities and regions" includes not only public authorities (municipalities, groups of municipalities, regional authorities, etc.), but also any organisation that is in charge of planning and operating waste and wastewater

management, such as public and private waste management companies. It is important to connect together organisations that can carry out or facilitate the implementation of circular bio-based solutions.

The definition of the target audience is clearly communicated on the website and on the communication materials developed for the promotion of the Network.

The HOOP Network of Cities and Regions will be materialised in the Urban Circular Bioeconomy Hub (UCBH), an online platform to foster knowledge exchange and replication in cities across Europe, which will be launched in 2022. The members of the HOOP Network will have a reserved place in the UCBH to follow up the development of the project, identify HOOP activities to which they can participate, and interact with one another.

One of the key priorities of the HOOP Network is to provide content to cities and regions, that is relevant to their interest. Therefore, it will be important to identify each participant's key interests, challenges, and local situations (in terms of local specificities, waste and wastewater practices and strategies, performances, etc.), so that the project's outcomes and activities are proposed in priority to territories that can directly benefit from them. A dedicated "tagging system" will be developed, to ease the identification of key characteristics and interests of the different users of the UCBH (waste collection, wastewater treatment sludge recovery, etc.) or challenges (e.g., densely populated cities, touristic areas, etc.).

3. The National Replication Workshops

3.1. What is a National Replication Workshop?

The engagement of local and national stakeholders is one of the core activities of the HOOP project, in order to promote the uptake of Urban Circular Bioeconomy in Europe. The Lighthouses have several possibilities to foster the stakeholders' engagement. For instance, the Biowaste Clubs (BC), events and meetings for multi-stakeholder engagement, are key to build a strong and informed stakeholder audience that can be part of the project and facilitate the development of a shared vision for the local bioeconomy.

By the end of the project, each Lighthouse has to take advantage of at least one of the Biowaste Clubs to organise a National Replication Workshop (NRW), which is an event to promote multi-stakeholder engagement. A NRW aims to involve other cities and regions at national level with a participatory approach. The main objective is to **promote the replication of the innovative systems and solutions** implemented in the Lighthouse Cities and Regions in other territories.

The NRWs are a good opportunity to involve the members of the HOOP Network of Cities and Regions, which represent the key actors for the replication of the project's findings.

There are several possible formats that could be chosen, alone or combined, to organize a NRW, for instance:

- **Conference:** an event mixing presentation and round-tables where various speakers can present their own experience and exchange views on key topic, with exchanges with the audience.
- **Workshop:** a meeting where participants engage in discussion on a specific topic.
- **Training session:** a session where participants are trained through courses and practical exercises on specific topics or activities relevant to their field of work.
- **Study visits:** a field visit to present a process, a unit, or any other aspects of an organisation or a company, element where visitors are explained the functioning (of a specific department, a collection system, a treatment process, etc.) and is able to interact with technicians and experts. In the case of HOOP, study visits might be on the biowaste collection system, or a pilot plant processing organic waste or wastewater sludge.

3.2. The objectives

The key objective of the National Replication Workshop is to promote the replication of the HOOP solutions to other cities and regions at national level. However, other objectives can be listed and adapted to the different Lighthouses, depending on their needs and challenges:

- Analyse current barriers related to the pilot activities (policy, economic framework, lack of expertise, social acceptance, etc.) and potential solutions;
- Develop a shared biowaste valorization vision at national level;
- Attract the attention of policy makers on the HOOP project and the Lighthouse involvement;
- Promote the involvement of the stakeholders of the Biowaste Clubs and secure their involvement in the future;
- Train other decision-makers and waste experts at national level about some of the more concrete aspects of the project.

When defining the content and the objective of a NRW, it is important to identify the opportunities of such event for the implementation of the HOOP project at national level (to draw attention of national policy makers on current legal barriers, promote the solution to potential organic waste producers on an innovative treatment process, etc.).

3.3. Stakeholders to be involved

The key target of a NRW is other cities and regions at national level, but other organisations can be involved and targeted as well: national authorities (i.e., ministry for environment or agriculture), national federations of industries, national association of public authorities, etc. Furthermore, the role that local decision-makers can play fostering the bioeconomy up in the local political agenda has also to be considered. The national stakeholders involved in the Biowaste Clubs can be contacted to suggest key stakeholders that could be interested in joining the NRW.

Lighthouses are invited to involve members of the HOOP Network of Cities and Regions present in their same country. These organisations are likely to be very interested in the HOOP activities and are key targets for the replication of HOOP outcomes. Nevertheless, the number of cities and regions involved might be limited according to the characteristics of the NRW (online or in presence).

If there is a national federation of cities and/or regions working on circular economy, bioeconomy, or any relevant topic, it can also be pertinent to engage in a collaboration (co-organisation of the NRW, promotion of the event, etc.) that could improve the reach and the impact of the event.

3.4. HOOP partners in support

The Lighthouses will be supported in the organisation of the NRW mainly by five HOOP partners:

- **Association of cities and regions for the sustainable resource management (ACR+)**: is an international network of cities and regions sharing the aim of promoting a sustainable resource management and accelerating the transition towards a circular economy on their territories and beyond. Circular economy calling for cooperation between all actors, ACR+ is open to other key players in the field of material resource management such as NGOs, academic institutions, consultancy or private organisations. ACR+ manages the HOOP Network of cities and regions.
- **Collaborating Centre on Sustainable Consumption and Production (CSCP)**: is a Think and Do tank that works with businesses, policy makers, partner organisations and civil society toward a sustainable planet. The United Nations Environment Program (UNEP) and the Wuppertal Institute for Climate, Energy and Environment jointly founded CSCP in 2005. As a non-for profit it focuses on the promotion of sustainable patterns of consumption and production (SCP). The CSCP adopts a holistic approach to foster SCP involving all actor groups and stakeholders. It has expertise in the areas of Products and Services, Cities & Infrastructure, Policy, Lifestyles & Behaviour and Business & Entrepreneurship.
- **Science for Change (SfC)**: is a Small and Medium Enterprise (SME) born from the will to tackle societal challenges affecting communities using innovative solutions. SfC specialises in developing user-centred, innovative services and products based on citizen science, participatory strategies, community engagement and co-creation processes to facilitate social innovation. It focuses on environmental issues affecting citizens, or any other matters of concern, and uses a methodology based on a quadruple helix model of stakeholder engagement (public authorities and policy makers, industries and SMEs, academia, and communities, NGOs and CSOs, amongst others), to promote dialogue, increase transparency, and to co-design innovative solutions that are relevant to all the stakeholders involved.
- **2GO OUT Consulting (2GOOUT)**: is a Consulting Company that provides specialized services to integrate sustainability & innovation actions into corporate strategy of their clients. 2GO OUT Consulting provides services in the field of ISO 50001 (Energy Management Systems), energy efficiency, low carbon energy, finance for sustainable energy, low carbon strategies, smart cities and communities strategies, ecoinnovative solutions and strategies. The company also support organizations to prepare and manage their research & innovation projects, including proposals submission to Horizon 2020 Programme.
- **Greenovate! Europe (GIE)**: is a non-profit network of eco-innovation experts. It pools 2000 technicians and 500 innovation advisors to provide a full range of eco -innovation services to accelerate the green transition. The members span the research and innovation value chain – from research centres through to innovation consultants and industrial clusters. The team in Brussels makes the connections and amplify the activities by engaging in EU wide knowledge transfer activities.

The expertise of the listed HOOP partners will be key to facilitate the organisation of a successful NRW. Thus, aside from this guide, a clear and smooth communication with the Lighthouses will be kept for the whole duration of the project.

The Lighthouses will be encouraged to involve other partners part of the HOOP consortium as experts depending on the topics addressed by each NRW (investment, urban metabolism, key technical aspects, social acceptance, etc.). Nevertheless, in order to avoid any kind of language barriers, the international experts might be supported a live interpretation, if the hosting Lighthouse decides to do it in its local language and in case the experts cannot speak the local language.

The cities and regions that joined the HOOP Network will already be connected with the Lighthouses following the launch of the UCBH. Furthermore, the tagging system (allowing members of the HOOP Network to list its main topics of interest) will provide the right match among the users in terms of topics addressed. Thus, the Lighthouses will have the opportunity to involve the members of the HOOP Network acting on the same topics, and possibly in the same country. The NRW will be a very good opportunity to reinforce the relationship among cities and regions acting at national level and to build together follow-ups based on the pilot cases.

4. How-to guide to organise a National Replication Workshop

This section is designed to support the HOOP Lighthouse Cities and Regions on how to plan, organise and implement successful National Replication Workshops. The steps and the examples provided are only suggestions and can be adapted to the local needs. During the designing phase of the NRW, the Lighthouses will be fully supported by the HOOP partners involved in this task.

The guide follows 7 steps which could be implemented with a different order depending from the case:

- Step 1: Define the key topics and objectives;
- Step 2: Identify the stakeholders;
- Step 3: Involve experts;
- Step 4: Define the format;
- Step 5: Draft the Agenda;
- Step 6: Promote the event;
- Step 7: Plan the results.

4.1. Step 1: Define the key topics and objectives

On this first step, the first question to be addressed is related to the main objective of the NRW: what do you want to obtain with the NRW? As stated before, the NRW can focus on the development of a shared bioeconomy strategy, or on the identification of solutions to the (legal, economic, technical, etc.) barriers met during the pilot cases. The identification of the main objective(s) will help in the choice of a specific format and, especially, in the definition of the stakeholders to involve.

Once the main objective has been defined, it is time to list the topic(s) of the NRW. Each Lighthouse will focus on the topics addressed during the project. For instance, if a Lighthouse wants to increase the quality level of the organic waste produced by domestic users, this same topic could be developed in several ways: by focusing on the citizens' engagement, or on technical solutions to improve the door-to-door collection, or by setting

specific controls during the collection. The Biowaste Clubs will be a good opportunity to start identifying the key sectors of interest.

The communication and the support provided by the HOOP partners will be crucial. ACR+ will coordinate with CSCP, 2GO OUT and SfC to assess the organization of the NRW in response of needs and suggestions arising during the Biowaste Clubs.

A set of different strategies that could be used to identify the objective(s) and topic(s) are listed as inspiration:

- **Organise brainstorming sessions to wrap up the Biowaste Clubs.** At the end of the meeting, plan an evaluation process to gather the main outcomes by the stakeholders involved. Encourage the participants to reflect on some questions that can provide feedback on which the objective and topic of the NRW can be based on. For instance: Which topics were more interesting for you? Which kind of follow-ups would you like to see developed? On which session did you learn the most? Which topics would you have liked to discuss? Etc.
- **Draft a first list of topics and organise working groups.** If the objective of the NRW is well defined, it will be easier to draft a list of topics. During the previous Biowaste Clubs meetings, divide the participants in working groups to discuss the selected topics. Each group could discuss about one of the topics or a rotation can be organised so that each participant addresses every topic. Collect the feedbacks and select the topic that could better meet the objective.
- **Involve the HOOP Network of Cities and Regions:** get in touch with the members of the HOOP Network located in your country to explore the main challenges that they face. This could also be a way to facilitate the involvement of the HOOP Network. Prepare an online survey and get in touch with them personally. For this task, ask for the support of ACR+.

The Biowaste Clubs meetings could provide very interesting ideas and solutions for the NRW so keep it in mind while planning their organisation.

4.2. Step 2: Identify the stakeholders

The identification of the stakeholders is based on the objective defined for the NRW. In general, the HOOP Network of Cities and Regions is the main target group since it gives the opportunity to involve cities and regions, of the same country, that are already facing challenges in terms of urban bioeconomy. Furthermore, some of the cities and regions involved can provide interesting solutions, or even open interesting questions.

Keeping in mind that the main objective of the NRW is to facilitate the replicability of the project's findings, some key stakeholders of the value chain have to be strongly involved:

- **National authorities:** to get the legal framework, planned national strategies and objectives, and possibly economic instruments;
- **Public authorities at regional and local level:** to facilitate the replication of the pilot cases and discuss the barriers and possible solution. For this type of stakeholder, the HOOP Network could represent a

relevant channel but Lighthouses are encouraged to take advantage of national networks of public authorities;

- **Companies working in the waste sector** (utility companies, consultancies, etc.): that might be interested in the topic or provide solutions. The NRW would be a great opportunity to put this kind of stakeholder in contact with the HOOP Network;
- **Companies acting as (bio)waste producers** (i.e., supermarkets) that could benefit of the innovative solutions implemented by the Lighthouses;
- **Potential investors;**
- **Research institutions and universities:** to get inspiration for the development of innovative solutions to overcome the barriers identified in the pilot cases;
- **National and local NGOs** that might be interested in the topic and collaborate on citizen engagement or social acceptance;
- **Existing working groups or organisations:** to promote the NRW among people and professionals already involved in the topic of bioeconomy.

Lighthouses can decide to target stakeholders beyond the national level (e.g. by also inviting organisations from neighbouring countries), if deemed interesting. However, the question of the language barrier should be kept in mind, and the topics addressed must also be relevant to foreign organisations.

4.3. Step 3: Involve experts

During the identification of the stakeholders, it is useful to also identify experts that could be involved in the NRW as speakers, trainers, or moderators. The HOOP partners will support the lighthouse cities and regions to list a selection of experts using a set of criteria:

- **Topic of expertise:** it needs to meet the topic defined for the NRW;
- **Location:** ACR+ has a budget to cover the travel costs of members of the HOOP Network that can participate as experts in the meeting. Also, each Lighthouse has a budget to cover such expenses.
- **Language:** in order to avoid language barriers, the experts that can speak the national language of the country where the NRW is organised, will be preferred. If this will not be possible, a live interpreter will have to be kept in mind while planning the budget.

Among the HOOP consortium, many partners could be considered to cover the role of expert, and can use their own budget to cover travel expenses. The HOOP consortium covers different steps of the value chain, from biowaste recovery to valorisation and characterization of the final products and unites complementary stakeholders with the deep multi -disciplinary knowledge crucial to PDA creation and the achievement of project objectives.

Depending on the format chosen, especially if you planned to register the event, you have to provide an informed consent form to the speakers that they must sign. ACR+ can provide such a consent form.

4.4. Step 4: Define the format

In order to reach the objective of fostering the replication of the HOOP findings, the NRW needs to be organised promoting a participative approach, an exchange of knowledge and profitable interactions among the stakeholders. In general, the format will be chosen based on: i) the topic identified for the NRW and ii) the stakeholders involved. Additionally, the “[Ladder of Citizen Participation](#)” of Sherry Arnstein could be a relevant source of inspiration to define the format for each NRW.

Nowadays, the first step to start drawing an appropriate format is related to the choice between a presential event and online event. This will depend on the national Covid19 restrictions since the people involved will mainly travel within the national borders. The presential events should be preferred in order to facilitate a participatory approach.

Some examples of participatory face-to-face and online formats are listed below grouped by session goals:

Introduce a topic:

Face-to-face:

Walkshop: Instead of introducing a topic by a traditional workshop, participants can walk to concrete points to discover the topic and gather relevant information. For example, before debating about circular urban metabolism, participants can visit key points of the city that are already tackling this challenge to explore the issue.

Digitally:

Virtual panels: This format gathers a group of experts introducing and exchanging ideas about a topic in front of a (virtual) audience. It can set the basis for a posterior discussion with the audience.

Get a better understanding of challenges, opportunities or perspectives:

Face-to face:

Card Sort: It is a quick and easy way to spark conversation about what matters most to the agents involved in a specific issue. By putting a deck of cards, each with a word or single image, in someone’s hands and then asking them to rank them in order of preference, you’ll gain huge insight into challenges and opportunities of a topic or participants’ perspectives of any issue.

Digitally:

Virtual World Café: Traditionally, the World Café methodology hosts small to large group dialogues about concrete topics in tables hosted in several informal places such as local libraries, coffee houses or neighbourhood bars. This simple, effective, and flexible format can be also translated in a virtual space by using virtual space tools where people can meet and talk such as [Wonder](#), [Gather.town](#) or [Remo](#).

Co-create solutions to a clearly defined challenge or reach an agreement:

Face-to-face:

[PlayDecide](#) is an open access card game to facilitate informed social debates around complex issues. It lets reaching an agreement through group consensus. Players can pick from more than 350 already made games in 28 languages covering a variety of topical issues. Moreover, they can create their own games through the website and then print them.

Digitally:

[Miro](#) is an online collaborative whiteboard platform to bring teams together and, among other multiple options, structure ideas and link them.

Evaluation

Face-to-face:

[Collective book](#): Lay out photographs and other collected material regarding the project (or anything that you want to evaluate, for example, a session or an event) and ask participants to select items to put on your evaluation book, encouraging them to add notes about how they felt at different points and where they gained new skills, knowledge, etc.

Digitally:

Virtual Survey tools like [Mentimeter](#) or [Slido](#) let you collect participants' feedback towards the end of a session.

The Biowaste Clubs can be used as a testing session of the different methodologies, training the stakeholders involved to be participative. The HOOP partners will support the Lighthouse Cities and Regions in the adaptation of the methodologies to their contexts and topics.

While choosing the format, there are some elements that can be considered to increase the participation:

- **Training sessions:** the NRW could be part of an existing training course in the field of bioeconomy. Otherwise, the training sessions could be held by the several experts that are part of the HOOP consortium, in order to increase the knowledge of these topics (e.g. fostering investments, developing a PDA, identifying treatment solutions, promoting social acceptance of waste collection, etc.). The training should focus on concrete aspects of the pilot case;
- **Study visits:** it would increase the participation of the stakeholders since, through the study visit, it is easier to explain and share the innovative solutions developed within the project. The study visit is also a good opportunity to facilitate the networking and the further collaboration among the stakeholders involved, and to showcase the local bioeconomy strategy in a concrete way.

A presential event needs to be planned with a duration of one to two days, especially if it includes a study visit and a practical demonstration. A 2-days event gives also the opportunity to plan a social dinner/lunch. This can become a very successful strategy to increase the participation of the stakeholders during the morning sessions of the NRW.

If a face-to-face event is not possible, the Lighthouses will have to choose an online conference platform based on the size of the audience planned and the objectives. A similar approach as in Biowaste Clubs organizations might be followed.

As mentioned before, there is a series of online platforms that can help to encourage the participation of the stakeholders and the collections of ideas and feedbacks:

- [Slido](#): a user-friendly platform to create polls and surveys that can show the results changing in life;
- [Mentimeter](#): an easy-to-use presentation software, which allows to create fun and interactive presentations. It can be used to create pools and surveys to engage the stakeholders in a creative way during the event.
- [Miro](#): an online collaborative whiteboarding platform that enables distributed teams to work effectively together, from brainstorming with digital sticky notes to planning and managing agile workflows.

On this phase, define the date based on the availability of the main stakeholders to involve and the experts. Keep also in mind to count at least 2 months for the promotion of the event. Once the date has been chosen, inform the HOOP partners to ask for their support.

4.5. Step 5: Draft the agenda

Once defined the experts to be involved, the format and the topics, draft the agenda keeping in mind some basic points:

- The “seminar” sessions designed as a traditional conference (a speaker in front of a silent audience) need to be avoided as much as possible or, at least, limited within 10 minutes for each speaker. Using a roundtable format, where each speaker is given a limited time for introduction, and then answer questions from the moderator or the audience, can lead to more interactive sessions. If roundtables or interactive sessions are foreseen, identify a moderator that is used to lead such session;
- Keep in count a break after max 2.5 hours, which can be a good opportunity for networking, so plan to have a coffee station;
- Alternate “learning mode” to participatory sessions where people are divided in smaller groups to work on the same topic;

4.6. Step 6: Promotion

The NRWs have to respect the HOOP visual identity and the H2020 programme must always be visualised. This part will mention the communication strategy pointing out to the importance of respecting both the project’s visual identity and the H2020 mentions.

Each Lighthouse has a specific budget for promotional material such as HOOP leaflets and merchandising.

The promotion strategy has to be defined based on three phases of the NRW:

- **Before the event**: start promoting the event in advance (4-6 months) launching a save-the-date. The Lighthouses will have the support of the official project channels (newsletter, social media and website). Nevertheless, since the NRW are organised at national level, it’s a good strategy to involve national-regional-local media, radio, newspaper and online magazines. In this phase, the Lighthouses will be

encouraged to take advantage of the Biowaste Clubs, the HOOP Network of Cities and Regions, and the HOOP communication channels to promote the event.

- **During the event:** in order to get visibility at national level, it is possible to invite the press or set a short press conference before or after the event, where local elected representatives and local experts could present the project and local bioeconomy strategy to the local press. It is also possible to plan interviews with the participants (in this case, informed consent forms will be required). Schedule the live-posting on social media, tagging the main stakeholders involved and describing the main moments of the event. As suggestion, schedule a post/tweet at the beginning of each section of the event, or to sum up the key messages of the different speakers (for instance: at the beginning, first speaker, first roundtable, working groups sessions, evaluation, interviews, closing words, etc.).
- **After the event:** publish a press release just after the end of the event (draft it in advance). Create videos using the interviews. Summing the topics discussed with an infographic is a very creative way to communicate the main outcomes of the event.

4.7. Step 7: The results

Have a clear idea of the practical results that the NRW should produce. For instance, it can be a good idea to produce videos and pictures of the event, for the following promotion of the project. In this case, a video-maker/photographer could be needed or find a profile within the project team, and the consent form will need to be provided to the participants.

Closing the event gathering an evaluation from the stakeholders could help other Lighthouses in the organisation of similar workshops, or to better understand the key topic of interest of the participants. The evaluation could be made with a short survey in order to collect quantitative data or with interviews. In this case, the interviews could be recorded and be used in future to promote the event. Focus the evaluation on the likely level of replicability reached.

In any case, make sure to have an attendance list that must be signed by participants, which will help to keep track of the actual participation, but also for the reporting to the H2020 project officer. Besides, a short summary (3 to 5-page long) must be drafted to provide a quick synthesis of the event and its main outcomes.

A list of data to collect is suggested below:

- Number of attendees;
- Sectors involved;
- Pictures;
- Short videos;
- Brainstorming clouds written on paper;
- Emails of people interested in the project (in accordance with the GDPR);

Part of these elements could be collected planning the attendees list that needs to be filled at the entrance of the event.

If the different speakers agree, make sure to publish the presentations and possible recording on your website, and to share them with the HOOP communication manager so that it can be published on the HOOP website as well. As mentioned previously, such publication requires the consent of the different participants.

The management of all the personal data collected before, during and after the event will have to be aligned with the GDPR and respect the principles of research with humans and personal data protection. HOOP partners are recommended to involve the contact person for ethics issues in their organisation to make sure that these requirements are taken into consideration, and to refer to HOOP deliverables on ethics requirement and the informed consent procedure.

The main outcomes of the National Replication Workshops will be gathered in a document that will be published in October 2024.

5. Conclusions

The organisation of the National Replication Workshops is key to ensure the right promotion of the project findings at national level, increasing as much as possible the opportunity of replication of the innovative solutions and strategies defined by the HOOP project.

The involvement of the members of the HOOP Network of Cities and Regions is a good opportunity to wide the audience and to gather other cities and regions facing the same challenges faced by the Lighthouses. This sort of engagement will be supported by ACR+, which is in charge of the management of the HOOP Network.

This report is a collection of inspirations and key points to guide the lighthouse cities and regions in the right organization of the NRW, in order to achieve the more from them. Although the strategies provided are just suggestions that each Lighthouse can adapt to the kind of workshop chosen and to the specific objectives, there some key points that should always be kept in mind and respect:

- The main goal of the NRWs is to promote the replication of the innovative systems and solutions implemented in the lighthouse cities and regions in other territories to promote multi-stakeholder engagement;
- The NRW aims to involve other cities and regions at national level with a participatory approach;
- The promotion of the event needs to follow the project identity and the EU requirements (e. g. visualise the EU flag and the disclaimer on the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme);
- The results of the NRWs need to be gathered and described in a summary that will be the base for the publication of the D8.7 Report summarising the results of the different NRWs, which will be public by October 2024. For this, the basic data on the participants will have to be collected, even if the level of information is left to the decision of each Lighthouse;
- Both the data and the multimedia materials collected during the NRWs have to respect the GDPR, providing in advance a consent for to the participants of the workshops, which explains in detail the use that the HOOP project will do of the data provided.

The organization of the NRW is a responsibility of each Lighthouse, which can always count on the support of the HOOP partners involved in this specific activity, as listed in the section 3.4. Nevertheless, the HOOP partners will encourage the Lighthouses to find the right format for the workshop to adapt to the national conditions and the number of participants. As long as the key points mentioned above are respected, Lighthouses are invited to be creative and opt for the format that fits the most their objective.

Each NRW will be promoted in the HOOP website and newsletter to allow everyone interested to take part in it.

6. References

- (1) The HOOP project: <https://hooproject.eu/>
- (2) The HOOP Network of Cities and Regions: <https://hooproject.eu/network/>
- (3) ACR+: <https://www.acrplus.org/en/>
- (4) Collaborating Centre on Sustainable Consumption and Production: <https://www.scp-centre.org/>
- (5) Science for Change: <https://www.scienceforchange.eu/>
- (6) Greenovate! Europe: <https://greenovate-europe.eu/>
- (7) Arnstein's Ladder of Citizen Participation: <https://www.citizenshandbook.org/arnsteinsladder.html>
- (8) Walkshop: <https://ccn.waag.org/drupal/sites/default/files/2018-03/WaagWalkshop.pdf>
- (9) Virtual panels: <https://trainingindustry.com/articles/professional-development/virtual-panels-10-tips-for-speakers-and-moderators/>
- (10) Card Sort: <https://www.designkit.org/methods/24>
- (11) Virtual World Café: <https://www.barbaracv.com/blog/how-to-organise-and-facilitate-a-virtual-world-cafe/>
- (12) PlayDecide: <https://playdecide.eu/>
- (13) Miro platform: <https://miro.com/>
- (14) Creative Evaluation Toolkit: <http://www.artworkscreative.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2015/11/Creative-Evaluation-Toolkit.pdf>
- (15) Slido platform: <https://www.sli.do/>
- (16) Mentimeter platform: <https://www.mentimeter.com/>

7. Annex

7.1. Checklist

ACTIVITY	SUGGESTED DEADLINE	WHO TO INVOLVE	STATUS*
Define the date (inform the HOOP partners)	4-6 months before (or during the previous Biowaste Club)	HOOP partners	
Define the objective of the event	4 months before (or during the previous Biowaste Club)	Participants of the Biowaste Clubs; HOOP network of cities and regions; HOOP partners	
Define the key topics	3 months before (or during the previous Biowaste Club)	Participants of the Biowaste Clubs; HOOP network of cities and regions; HOOP partners	
Define the stakeholders and the target	3 months before	Participants of the Biowaste Clubs; HOOP network of cities and regions; HOOP partners	
Define the format	2 months before (or during the previous Biowaste Club)	HOOP partners (mainly Science for Change)	
Find a moderator (if needed)	2 months before		
Find a video-maker for interviews and a photographer (if needed)	1.5 months before		

D8.3 GUIDANCE FOR THE ORGANISATION OF NATIONAL REPLICATION WORKSHOPS

Find the venue and the catering (if not online)	2 months before		
Launch a save the date to start engaging participants	2 months before	HOOP partners (mainly Greenovate and ACR+ to use HOOP communication channels); HOOP network of cities and regions	
Invite the external experts (support by HOOP partners) and high-level speakers	2 months before	HOOP partners	
Draft the agenda	1.5 months before	HOOP partners	
List the materials needed (check the budget for communication)	1.5 months before		
Send informed consent forms to the speakers	1 month before	Ask to Greenovate for the consent form	
Plan the non-formal dinner/lunch	1 month before	Speakers, participants, HOOP partners	
Publish the final agenda	1 month before	HOOP partners (mainly Greenovate and ACR+ to use HOOP communication channels)	
Contact the local media for a press conference	2 weeks before	Local media and press	
Prepare attendance list	1 week before		

D8.3 GUIDANCE FOR THE ORGANISATION OF NATIONAL REPLICATION WORKSHOPS

Collect inform consent forms from speakers	On the day of the event	Speakers	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Issue a press release	On the day of the event	Local media and press	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Send a message to thank the speakers	One week after the event		<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Prepare a short summary of the event	Two weeks after event		<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>

*Check the square based on the status of the activity:

- Just started
- Ongoing
- Completed

7.2. The HOOP partners

HOOP partner	Description	Field of expertise
CETENMA (Technology Centre for Energy and Environment)	A private, non-profit Business Association that supports companies with technological research, development and innovation in all areas relating to Energy and the Environment, thereby assisting them in becoming more competitive.	Water, Waste treatment, Bioenergy, Renewable Energies and Energy Efficiency, Innovation and technology transfer
ITENE (Instituto Tecnológico del Embalaje, Transporte y Logística) Technical Institute of Packaging, Transport and Logistics)	A non-profit research centre specialized in packaging technologies, transport, logistics and circular economy.	Research and development, Innovation, Tests and advanced services, Market research and R&D Management
SAV (S.A. Agricultores de la Vega de Valencia)	A large company that conducts its activity in the environmental sector, from Gardening, agriculture, preservation of natural parks, logistic, street cleaning, and integral waste management to water treatment plant maintenance.	Innovation in waste life cycle
DRAXIS Environmental S.A.	A dynamic company that focuses on providing specialised environmental consultation services and developing real life environmental ICT solutions.	Circular economy, waste management, sustainable agriculture, air quality and government.
NAFIGATE Corporation, a.s	A Czech technological company focused on nanofiber applications and biotechnology. The company brings to the global market projects aimed at developing a new energy-efficient generation of nanofiber membranes for water and air purification technologies.	Zero Waste Management; Circular Economy; High-Added Value Materials that are produced by residues transformation; Life Cycle Assessment, material engineering and biodegradability testing
CETAQUA (Fundación Centro Gallego de Investigaciones del Agua)	A technology center which manages and executes research and development projects aiming at ensuring the sustainability and efficiency of the water cycle	Characterization of sludge, wastewater and waste and sample analysis; extraction, anaerobic digestion,

	management by creating new products and innovative solutions for industries, public administrations and society.	membranes, biofilm and granular aerobic sludge treatment, ultrasonic assisted equipment, sorption, milling.
Research4Life B.V.	A dynamic research and consulting firm devoted to the development and evaluation of food production, bioenergy, and biobased products.	Bio-based and bioenergy use opportunities; Valorization of residues and waste streams source as biobased feedstocks and crop nutrients
ACR+ (Association of Cities and Regions for Sustainable Resource Management)	An international network of cities and regions sharing the aim of promoting a sustainable resource management.	Prevention at source, reuse and recycling, accelerating the transition towards a circular economy; effective waste-product-resource policies.
Greenovate! Europe	A non-profit network of eco-innovation experts.	Eco - innovation services; bioeconomy, circular economy and sustainable cities
Science for Change	An SME born from the will to tackle societal challenges affecting communities using innovative solutions.	Development of user-centered, innovative services and products based on citizen science; participatory strategies; community engagement and co-creation processes to facilitate social innovation.
2 GO OUT (Sustentepopeia Unipessoal, Lda)	A Consulting Company that provides specialized services to integrate sustainability and innovation actions into corporate strategy of their clients.	ISO 50001 (Energy Management Systems), energy efficiency, low carbon energy, finance for sustainable energy, low carbon strategies, smart cities and communities strategies, eco-innovative solutions and strategies.
CSCP (Collaborating Centre on Sustainable Consumption and Production GmbH)	Think and Do tank that works with businesses, policy makers, partner	Products and Services, Cities & Infrastructure, Policy, Lifestyles &

	organizations and civil society toward a sustainable planet.	Behavior and Business & Entrepreneurship.
RdA (RdA Climate Solutions Unipessoal Lda)	An advisory boutique specialized in mitigation and adaptation strategies with special expertise in clean energy and sustainable finance.	Project structuring, sustainable finance, and project and policy evaluation.
Bax & Company	A sustainable innovation facilitating company that supports governments (national, regional, municipal), enterprises (large, medium and small sized) and clusters / sector associations in the ideation, development, piloting and mainstreaming of innovative sustainable businesses.	Advances materials, Blockchain, Circular Economy, Climate Adaptation, Future mobility, Industry 4.0, Livable cities, Smart cities, Urban energy.
BEDIN SARA	She operates at European level as expert on demand-side innovation policy and innovation public procurement and consultant for the Public Sector on innovation and IPRs management.	Innovation procurement methodology and implementation.